

9-Acridone-4-carboxylic acid : Crystal structure, immune-fluorescence detection of viral antigen and cell imaging studies

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Abstract : 9-Acridone-4-carboxylic acid has been established as a cheap, non-carcinogenic fluorescence dye. It can differentiate living and dead cells in a eukaryotic microbial population viz. *Candida* sp. Moreover, the dye has been tagged with specific antibody (Ab) without compromising its fluorescence property and used for detection of specific antigen in natural samples. The dye crystallizes in the monoclinic space group *C2/c* with unit cell dimensions : $a = 17.7608(10)$ Å, $b = 7.3009(4)$ Å and $c = 16.7328(9)$ Å while other unit cell parameters are : $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 103.093(4)^\circ$, $\gamma = 90^\circ$, $V = 2113.3(2)$ Å³ and $Z = 8$. The dye is soluble in HEPES buffer at pH 7.4.

Keywords : Acridone, crystal, dye, DNA, cell imaging.

Introduction

Acridone alkaloids, isolated from various plant sources are known to possess varieties of biological activities including anticancer, antitumor and ant-malarial properties¹⁻³. Moreover, acridone derivatives have analytical applications⁴.

Fluorescence based techniques are valuable tools to investigate cellular structure, function and interactions of bio-molecules. It is widely used in the determination of nucleic acids and proteins by gel electrophoresis and microarray techniques. Till date, most of the fluorescent dyes used in biological systems to visualize cell and different cell organelles are carcinogenic in nature⁵. Herein, we have reported the crystal structure and application of a very cheap, non-carcinogenic fluorescent dye, 9-acridone-4-carboxylic acid. It is soluble in HEPES buffer at pH 7.4. Fluorescence microscopic study shows that the dye is very effective for studying living cells including microbial populations in natural and laboratory samples. Additionally, the dye can be tagged with spe-

cific antibody (Ab) without negotiating its fluorescence property. The dye tagged Ab is useful for detection of specific antigen in clinical samples. Spectrophotometric studies of the complex between the fluorescent dye and different biomolecules like antibody (Ab, which is protein in nature), DNA and lipid have revealed significant shift of the absorption peak of dye-Ab complex over their individual absorption spectrum indicating a fair binding of the dye with the tested Ab. All the species were incubated in buffer environment for 6 h at 4 °C. The dye bound Ab (hereafter Ab^{dye}) has been tested against specific antigen (Ag). Newly formed Ag-Ab^{dye} complex has been detected by exposing the complex under UV illumination. This Ab^{dye} may be used in dye linked immune-sorbent assay for the detection of microbial Ag/Ab in clinical samples.

Material and methods :

2-Chloro benzoic acid (Alfa Aesar, India) and anthranilic acid (SRL, India) were purchased and used as received. All other chemicals and solvents were of analyti-

cal grade and used without further purification. Milli-Q 18.2 MΩ cm⁻¹ conductivity purification system (Bedford, MA, USA) water was used throughout all the experiments. JE virus has been supplied Thermo Scientific, India. Absorption and fluorescence spectra were recorded on Shimadzu Multi Spec 1501 absorption spectrophotometer and Hitachi F-4500 fluorescence spectrophotometer, respectively. Fluorescence imaging system was comprised of an inverted fluorescence microscope (Leica DM 1000 LED), digital compact camera (Leica DFC 420C) and an image processor (Leica Application Suite v3.3.0).

Synthesis of the dye :

Scheme 1 shows the Ullmann condensation of 2-chlorobenzoic acid with 2-aminobenzoic acid followed by cyclization in presence of sulfuric acid, to produce 9-acridone-4-carboxylic acid⁶.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of the dye (i) K₂CO₃, Cu powder, (ii) conc. H₂SO₄, 100 °C.

Determination of single crystal X-ray structure :

A single crystal of the dimension 0.14 mm × 0.13 mm × 0.06 mm was chosen for X-ray diffraction study. Crystallographic measurement has been performed at 100(2) K, while the X-ray crystal data are collected with a STOE IPDS-II two-circle diffractometer. Intensities are corrected for Lorentz polarization and absorption. The structures are solved by direct methods. Hydrogen atoms bound to carbon are idealized. Structural refinements have been performed with full-matrix least-squares based on *F*² by using the program SHELXL⁷. The goodness-of-fit on *F*² is 1.002. The molecular structure is developed using ORTEP III⁸. Hydrogen atoms are mostly discernible in difference Fourier maps and could be refined to reasonable geometry. Crystal structure and packing diagram of the dye are shown in Fig. 1. Crystal parameters and refinement factors of the dye are given in Table 1. Bond lengths and angles of the dye are presented in Table 2 and Table 3 respectively. Hydrogen bonding interactions has been shown in Table 4. CCDC 804363 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for the molecule.

Description of the structure :

The dye crystallizes in the monoclinic space group C2/c. The atom numbering scheme is given in Fig. 1. All bond distances and angles are normal and in good agreement with the similar reported acridone based compound⁹. The C(8)=O(18) bond length of 1.243(3) Å, conforms to the value for a carbonyl double bond, while the C(7)-

Fig. 1. (A) ORTEP view (50% thermal ellipsoid) and (B) crystal packing along a axis.

Table 1. Structural parameters of the dye

Empirical formula	C ₁₄ H ₉ NO ₃
Formula weight	239.22
Temperature	100(2) K
Wavelength	0.71073 Å
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	C2/c
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 17.7608(10)$ Å, $b = 7.3009(4)$ Å, $c = 16.7328(9)$ Å $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 103.093(4)^\circ$, $\gamma = 90^\circ$
Volume	2113.3(2) Å ³
Z	8
Density (calculated)	1.504 Mg/m ³
Absorption coefficient	0.107 mm ⁻¹
F(000)	992
Crystal size	0.14 × 0.13 × 0.06 mm ³
Theta range for data collection	2.35 to 26.37°
Index ranges	-22 ≤ h ≤ 21, 0 ≤ k ≤ 9, 0 ≤ l ≤ 20
Reflections collected	17099
Independent reflections	2162 [R(int) = 0.0772]
Completeness to theta = 26.37°	100.0%
Absorption correction	Semi-empirical from equivalents
Max. and min. transmission	0.9910 and 0.8787
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F ²
Data/restraints/parameters	2162/0/171
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.002
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	R1 = 0.0532, wR2 = 0.1180
R indices (all data)	R1 = 0.1067, wR2 = 0.1471
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.255 and -0.264 e.Å ⁻³

C(8) bond length of 1.452(3) Å and C(9)-C(8) bond length of 1.452(4) Å conforms to the value for a single bond, like in similar Schiff base compounds⁹, the bond lengths N(1)-C(2) and N(1)-C(14) are 1.367(3) and 1.378(3) respectively. The bond lengths C(15)-O(16) and C(15)-O(17) are 1.222(3) and 1.321(3) respectively conform to the value for a single bond and a double bond of carboxylic acid group. The bond angles H(1)-N(1)-C(14) and H(1)-N(1)-C(2) are 123.9(17) and 113.0(17) respectively, consistent with the *sp*² hybrid character of N(1) center. Moreover, the O(16)-C(15)-O(17) bond angle is 122.5(2), indicating the *sp*² hybrid character of C(15) center.

Dye-macromolecule interaction :

Interaction of protein (Ab)/DNA/lipid with the dye

Table 2. Bond lengths (Å) of the dye

Bond distances	(Å)	Bond distances	(Å)
N(1)-C(2)	1.361(3)	C(8)-C(9)	1.452(4)
N(1)-C(14)	1.318(3)	C(9)-C(10)	1.407(3)
N(1)-H(1)	0.96(3)	C(9)-C(14)	1.409(3)
C(2)-C(7)	1.412(3)	C(10)-C(11)	1.376(4)
C(2)-C(3)	1.419(3)	C(10)-H(10)	0.9500
C(3)-C(4)	1.384(4)	C(11)-C(12)	1.400(4)
C(3)-C(15)	1.483(3)	C(11)-H(11)	0.9500
C(4)-C(5)	1.390(4)	C(12)-C(13)	1.368(4)
C(4)-H(4)	0.9500	C(12)-H(12)	0.9500
C(5)-C(6)	1.361(4)	C(13)-C(14)	1.403(3)
C(5)-H(5)	0.9500	C(13)-H(13)	0.9500
C(6)-C(7)	1.400(4)	C(15)-O(16)	1.221(3)
C(6)-H(6)	0.9500	C(15)-O(17)	1.321(3)
C(7)-C(8)	1.452(3)	O(17)-H(17)	1.11(4)
C(8)-O(18)	1.243(3)		

Table 3. Bond angles (°) of the dye

Bond angles	(°)	Bond angles	(°)
C(2)-N(1)-C(14)	122.9(2)	C(7)-C(8)-C(9)	116.7(2)
C(2)-N(1)-H(1)	113.0(17)	C(10)-C(9)-C(14)	118.5(2)
C(14)-N(1)-H(1)	123.9(17)	C(10)-C(9)-C(8)	121.6(2)
N(1)-C(2)-C(7)	119.4(2)	C(14)-C(9)-C(8)	119.9(2)
N(1)-C(2)-C(3)	121.3(2)	C(11)-C(10)-C(9)	120.8(2)
C(7)-C(2)-C(3)	119.3(2)	C(11)-C(10)-H(10)	119.6
C(4)-C(3)-C(2)	118.8(2)	C(9)-C(10)-H(10)	119.6
C(4)-C(3)-C(15)	120.5(2)	C(10)-C(11)-C(12)	119.5(3)
C(1)-C(3)-C(15)	120.6(2)	C(10)-C(11)-H(11)	120.3
C(3)-C(4)-C(5)	122.0(2)	C(12)-C(11)-H(11)	120.3
C(3)-C(4)-H(4)	119.0	C(13)-C(12)-C(11)	121.4(3)
C(5)-C(4)-H(4)	119.0	C(13)-C(12)-H(12)	119.3
C(6)-C(5)-C(4)	119.0(3)	C(11)-C(12)-H(12)	119.3
C(6)-C(5)-H(5)	120.5	C(12)-C(13)-C(14)	119.3(2)
C(4)-C(5)-H(5)	120.5	C(12)-C(13)-H(13)	120.3
C(5)-C(6)-C(7)	121.7(2)	C(14)-C(13)-H(13)	120.3
C(5)-C(6)-H(6)	119.2	N(1)-C(14)-C(13)	119.4(2)
C(7)-C(6)-H(6)	119.2	N(1)-C(14)-C(9)	120.3(2)
C(6)-C(7)-C(2)	119.1(2)	O(13)-C(14)-C(9)	120.4(2)
C(6)-C(7)-C(8)	120.1(2)	O(16)-C(15)-O(17)	122.5(2)
C(2)-C(7)-C(8)	120.8(2)	O(16)-C(15)-C(3)	124.6(2)
O(18)-C(8)-C(7)	120.9(2)	O(17)-C(15)-C(3)	112.9(2)
O(18)-C(8)-C(9)	122.4(2)	O(15)-O(17)-H(17)	110.5(19)

has been studied by comparing the absorption spectra of the free species (biomolecules and free dye) to that of

Table 4. Torsion angles (°) for dye

C(14)-N(1)-C(2)-C(7)	-2.0(4)
C(14)-N(1)-C(2)-C(3)	177.7(2)
N(1)-C(2)-C(3)-C(4)	179.6(2)
C(7)-C(2)-C(3)-C(4)	-0.7(3)
N(1)-C(2)-C(3)-C(15)	-1.9(4)
C(7)-C(2)-C(3)-C(15)	177.8(2)
C(2)-C(3)-C(4)-C(5)	0.6(4)
C(15)-C(3)-C(4)-C(5)	-178.0(2)
C(3)-C(4)-C(5)-C(6)	-0.1(4)
C(4)-C(5)-C(6)-C(7)	-0.2(4)
C(5)-C(6)-C(7)-C(2)	0.0(4)
C(5)-C(6)-C(7)-C(8)	179.7(2)
N(1)-C(2)-C(7)-C(6)	-179.8(2)
C(3)-C(2)-C(7)-C(6)	0.4(3)
N(1)-C(2)-C(7)-C(8)	0.4(3)
C(3)-C(2)-C(7)-C(8)	-179.3(2)
C(6)-C(7)-C(8)-O(18)	2.0(4)
C(2)-C(7)-C(8)-O(18)	-178.3(2)
C(6)-C(7)-C(8)-C(9)	-177.9(2)
C(2)-C(7)-C(8)-C(9)	1.8(3)
O(18)-C(8)-C(9)-C(10)	-1.2(4)
C(7)-C(8)-C(9)-C(10)	178.7(2)
O(18)-C(8)-C(9)-C(14)	177.5(2)
C(7)-C(8)-C(9)-C(14)	-2.6(3)
C(14)-C(9)-C(10)-C(11)	0.4(4)
C(8)-C(9)-C(10)-C(11)	179.1(2)
C(9)-C(10)-C(11)-C(12)	-1.3(4)
C(10)-C(11)-C(12)-C(13)	1.3(4)
C(11)-C(12)-C(13)-C(14)	-0.2(4)
C(2)-N(1)-C(14)-C(13)	-179.5(2)
C(2)-N(1)-C(14)-C(9)	1.2(4)
C(12)-C(13)-C(14)-N(1)	180.0(2)
C(12)-C(13)-C(14)-C(9)	-0.8(4)
C(10)-C(9)-C(14)-N(1)	180.0(2)
C(8)-C(9)-C(14)-N(1)	1.2(4)
C(10)-C(9)-C(14)-C(13)	0.7(4)
C(8)-C(9)-C(14)-C(13)	-178.0(2)
C(4)-C(3)-C(15)-O(16)	-178.3(3)
C(2)-C(3)-C(15)-O(16)	3.2(4)
C(4)-C(3)-C(15)-O(17)	2.3(3)
C(2)-C(3)-C(15)-O(17)	-176.2(2)

their respective adduct after incubating for six hours in buffer medium. 30 μL of cod liver oil (1 mg mL^{-1})/herring sperm DNA (1 mg mL^{-1})/Ab (goat Ig G, approx. 1 mg mL^{-1}) and 10 μL dye (1 mg mL^{-1}) were individu-

Table 5. Hydrogen bonds for the dye (Å)

D-H...A	d(D-H)	d(H...A)	d(D...A)	<(DHA)
N(1)-H(1)...O(16)	0.96(3)	1.87(3)	2.669(3)	139(2)
O(17)-H(17)...O(18)#1	1.11(4)	1.52(4)	2.538(2)	149(3)

Symmetry transformations used to generate equivalent atoms :
#1 x+1/2,y+1/2,z

ally diluted to 3.0 mL (with HEPES buffer at pH 7.4) and measured their individual absorption spectra. In a separate set, each of the biomolecules (30 μL from 1 mg mL^{-1} stock) was mixed with 10 μL (1 mg mL^{-1}) dye and incubated for six hours and recorded the absorption spectrum of each biomolecule-dye adduct (after dilution to 3 mL with the same buffer). Results presented in Fig. 2A clearly indicate significant interaction between the dye and cod liver oil bio-molecule.

We have further tested the binding of the dye with specific Ab. For this purpose, the dye (30 μL from 1 mg mL^{-1} stock solution) was incubated with same amount of Ab for JE viral E protein (monoclonal Ab raised against E-protein of JE virus)¹⁰ for six hours and absorption spectrum of Ab-dye mixture is compared with the individual absorption spectrum of Ab and dye. Fig. 2B shows the significant interaction between the dye and the JE specific Ab.

Similarly interaction of the dye molecule with DNA has been presented in Fig. 2C.

The Ab-dye adduct was then precipitated from the reaction mixture using chilled acetone and washed thrice with chilled acetone to remove unbound free dye. The precipitate was vacuum dried to remove acetone and dissolved in HEPES buffer (pH 7.4) and kept at 4 °C for future use.

Dye-antibody interaction has been studied using fluorescence spectroscopy (Fig. 3). Significant quenching of emission intensity of the dye has been observed upon addition of antibody. A control experiment has also been performed using double distilled sterilized water instead of antibody where no significant quenching has been found.

Dye linked sandwich immunosorbent assay :

Use of dye bound Ab for the detection of JE virion in clinical samples, dye linked sandwich immune-sorbent

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of (A) Dye (10 μL) [purple], cod liver oil dye = (30 + 10) μL [blue], cod liver oil = 30 μL [red], in HEPES buffer (pH 7.4). (B) Dye 10 μL [purple], antibody and dye = (30 + 10) μL [red], antibody = 30 μL [blue], in HEPES buffer (pH 7.4). (C) Dye 10 μL [red], DNA and dye = (30 + 10) μL [black], DNA 30 μL [blue], in HEPES buffer (pH 7.4).

Fig. 3. Fluorescence spectra of the dye (10 μL), antibody (30 μL) and antibody-dye (30 μL + 10 μL), ($\lambda_{\text{Ex}} = 408 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{Em}} = 498 \text{ nm}$) in HEPES buffer (pH 7.4).

assay has been performed with the isolated dye complex (*supra*). Wells of a microtitre plate were coated with 25 μL of antibody by incubating one hour at ambient tem-

perature in humid condition and the excess antibodies were removed by washing with HEPES buffer saline. The empty space of the wells was blocked with 5% skimmed milk in HEPES buffer saline (pH 7.4, blocking buffer) to prevent nonspecific binding of Ag or Ab-dye complex in subsequent steps. After washing suspension supplied JE antigen (25 μL) was added in the test well, sterile buffer was added in the well as negative control and then the microtitre plate was incubated for one hour in humid box. After incubation, each well was washed thrice with 100 μL HEPES buffer containing 0.05% Tween-20. 25 μL of the dye tagged antibody conjugate was added to each well and incubated for one hour at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a humid chamber. After incubation each well of the microtitre plate was washed thrice with 100 μL HEPES buffer saline (pH 7.4) to remove the unbound dye-labeled monoclonal antibody and then the microtitre plate was read using a ELISA plate reader as well as

Fig. 4. Immuno-fluorescence-microscopy of Antigen-dye tagged antibody complex under 40X objective (400X magnification).

observed under high power magnification (40X) of a fluorescence microscope (LEICA DM 1000). Fig. 4 shows Ag-Ab-dye complex formation in positive well that fluoresce upon exposure to UV light.

Cell staining application :

Candida albicans (IMTECH No. 3018) and *Bacillus thuringiensis* cells were taken from exponentially growing culture in yeast extract glucose broth medium (pH 6.0, incubation temperature, 37 °C) and nutrient broth (pH 7.2, incubation temperature, 37 °C) respectively and separately centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min, washed twice with 0.1 M HEPES buffer at pH 7.4. The cells were then treated with the dye solution (1 mg mL⁻¹) in 0.1 M HEPES buffer, pH 7.4 for 60 min containing 0.01 % Triton X-100 as permeability enhancing agent. After incubation the cells were again washed with HEPES buffer at pH 7.4 and mounted on grease free glass slide to observe under a Leica DM 1000 fluorescence microscope equipped with UV filter¹¹. Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 reveal that the dye added cells emit significant fluorescence and thus, their morphology can be studied under high power magnification of a fluorescence microscope.

Differentiation of dead and living cell :

The dye is useful to differentiate living cells from dead cells in a eukaryotic microbial population. The

Fig. 5. *Bacillus thuringiensis* – incubated with dye (A) fluorescence microscope picture, (B) simple microscope, (C) control i.e. only cells without dye.

Fig. 6. *Candida albicans* – incubated with dye (A) fluorescence microscope picture, (B) simple microscope, (C) control i.e. only cells without dye.

nucleus is distinctly stained by the dye in a living cell, which is absent in the dead cell (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. *Candida albicans* incubated with dye (enlarged view).

Conclusion

Single crystal X-ray structure of 9-acridone-4-carboxylic acid has been reported. The molecule has been used as a novel fluorescence dye to determine the ratio of viable

and non-viable cells in a particular growth phase of microbial population which is particularly important in microscopic study of food samples and bacterial growth study. Most of the commercially available fluorescence dye tagged antibody based kits for the detection of viral¹² and other microbial antigens in clinical samples are costly and time consuming procedure, whereas the use of present dye seems to be much cheaper and faster.

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